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The comparison between emotional and informational support: A case study of Shiou Faction in Taiwan

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Abstract

Lion dance represented carrying favorable luck to individuals. After the patriot government moved to Taiwan, the inhabitants of the Guangdong Province brought the neighborhood originalities of society exercises (Lion dance) back to Taiwan. Endlessly had effectively opened up the exposure had coordinated a Shiou Faction Lion Dance bunch in Taiwan. By underlining individuals situated advancement, which will cover subjects of social mental learning hypothesis and the four parts of social help. Figuring out how much thickness the people cooperate with one another's, with the assistance of interpersonal organization investigation and chart. The object is to figure out which social help can lead the gathering to be fortitude, and which backing is awesome for the Shiou Faction Lion Dance association.

Keywords: Triadic Reciprocal Determinism; Social Cognitive Learning Theory; Social Network Diagram; Social Support

1. Introduction

The Chinese lion dance is a traditional dance that usually appeared in a religious or cultural festival. Most likely to be seen on an important occasion, for example, special events or ceremonies. The origin of the lion dance can be traced back to the Han Dynasty. Where back in the Chinese culture, the lion symbolized power, wisdom, and superiority [1]. As for the lion dance, it symbolized bringing good fortune to people. The introduction of the lion dance (beast dance), can be seen in other Asian countries. Such as Taiwan, where there are two periods, one during the Ming and Qing Dynasties and the other one during the Japanese Occupation Period. After the nationalist government moved to Taiwan, the residents of the Guangdong Province brought the local originalities of folk activities (Lion dance) back to Taiwan. And had successfully opened up the Guangdong lions market in Taiwan. The successful publicity organized a group that consists of 15 members naming themselves the Shiou Faction Lion Dance in Taiwan. Shiou Faction Lion Dance organization members believe that the concept of the lion dance is not just about movement skills. But it's more about focusing on the interconnection of how people-oriented development is being presented. This paper will focus on two different topics, one is about the idea of the three types of triadic reciprocal determinism and another one is about the four aspects of social support.

Therefore, to find out the result, this paper will conduct a semi-structured interview method as well as use social network analysis to conclude the data. The reason for using social network analysis is because a social network is an interactive relationship between members of a group, in which members are each other's external environment, based on the interaction between people, and the establishment of common values between groups [2]. Additionally, the main purpose of this paper is to use social network analysis data to prove that knowing the understanding of the triadic

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reciprocal determinism and the four aspects of social support does lead the Shiou Faction Lion Dance organization members to be united.

2. The Idea of the Triadic Reciprocal Determinism

According to [3], behavior, internal personal factors, and environmental influences all operate as interlocking determinants of each other; where reciprocal determinism was treated as a basic principle for analysing psychosocial phenomena at varying levels of complexity, ranging from intrapersonal development to interpersonal behavior, to the interactive functioning of organizational and societal systems. Where in the case of the Shiou Faction Lion Dance, they emphasize people-oriented development. The social cognitive learning theory emphasizes the idea of the three elements of triadic reciprocal determinism (Personal Factors, Behavioural Factors, and Environmental Factors). That can be found in Table 1, which described the details of what the three types of triadic reciprocal determinism mean.

Table 1 Three types of triadic reciprocal determinism

Personal (Individual) Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self- observation • Expectations • Attributions
Behavioral Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achievement • Self- efficacy • Capability
Environmental Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External factors • Feedback • Social norms

Moreover, [4], stated that the cognitive theory views human functioning as the product of the dynamic interplay of personal, behavior, and environmental influences. In Figure 1, shows the connection between each factor.

Figure 1 Triadic Reciprocal Determination through the Dynamic Interplay of Personal, Behavioral, and Environmental Factors [4]

Figure 1, shows the acquaintance between the following three factors: Personal Factors, Behavioral Factors, and Environmental Factors. That the most important is that there's a multiple-way of interactions. Yet, there is also an existence of a decision-influence relationship. That each factor had intercourse, for instance, that personal (Individual) factors may be affected by the environment and behavior, while the environmental factors will also be affected by the behavior and individuals and as for the behavior factors it will also be affected by the individuals and the environment. It clearly shows the main purpose of why interconnection between each factor is so relevant. Not to mention, among the factors, the environmental factor is recalled for being external. That is related to social support. Which are under the four aspects, and they are Emotional support, Appraisal support, Informational support, and Instrumental support.

3. The Shiou Faction Lion Dance under the Four Social Support

The Xiu Faction is a branch group of the lions in Taiwan and Guangxi. As a group in the field of winged serpents and lions, for them to upgrade the capacity of lion expressions, abilities, and gathering solidarity is vital. Preparing themselves in accordance with worldwide norms, needed to lead them to comprehend that bunch fortitude is significant, particularly with regards to finishing things together. The association individuals, occasionally have upgraded the capacity for passing the lion expressions and abilities to the following ages. Simultaneously, showing their individuals the effect of the four social help. According to [5], mention that social support is one of the important functions of social relationships; social support is always intended by the sender to be helpful, thus distinguishing it from intentional negative interactions (such as angry criticism, hassling, undermining). Together, [6] classified social support into four aspects: emotional support, evaluative (appraisal) support, informational support, and instrumental support. This can be viewed in Table 2 [6], had categorized the four different types of social support accordingly to definitions.

Table 2 Types of Social Support [6]

Types of Social Support	Definitions
Emotional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can provide empathy, self- esteem, care and trust to the supporter
Instrumental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can provide the supporter with substantial material, labour, money and assistance to improve the environment
Informational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can give the supporter an inner advice
Evaluative / Appraisal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can give the supporter positive feedback

To be more inconsistent, having major areas of strength for a design originates from the continuous social communications between different gatherings is what this paper planned to zero in on. Inside the four different social help, this paper intended to make an examination between Emotional help and Informational Support. The justification for picking this two rather than different ones. Is that Emotional help is tied in with communicating confidence, by getting care from dear loved ones. While the other one Informational help is tied in with getting exhortation and ideas as it were. There is no particular objective wishing whom to offer the perspective.

In addition, because of four unique aspects furthermore, every individual from the gathering has various attributes while confronting their companions, and will be treated in various ways because of various outer ecological circumstances, the informal organization framed will likewise be unique. As a result, this paper will be using social network analysis to prove that in the folklore theory that the members of the group knowing each other better and interacting more than outsiders will make the group stronger in the long run [7].

4. Methodology

To investigate, this paper will conduct a semi-structured interview, with a total of 15 members coming from the dragon and lion troupe. The process of the semi-structured interview was designed to answer the social support relationship between yourself and other members. During the process, there will be 14 males and 1 female in total. After gathering all the answers, it will be converted into a single 15 x 15 matrix format. Which will later be using SPSS version 22 for users to analyze and calculate the basic questions. Covered the gender, annual income of the dragon and lion troupe, license, the position whether the head of the group is full-time or not, and lastly the average and standard deviation of the number of permanent disciples and seniority.

Furthermore, to insist on the difference between emotional support and informational support, this paper will be using a social network diagram to show the relationship of each member. With the help of social network analysis, as the social support of external factors, using the social network method to analyze can also observe the social situation from a new perspective. [8] Pointed out that the analysis through the social network methods opens up a new way of analysis for social cognitive theory.

5. Results and discussion

After conducting a semi-structured interview, this paper used SPSS version 22 to analyze the data. Table 3, showed the gender distribution of the subjects in this study was 14 males and 1 female. With a total of having 15.13 average annual income, with a standard deviation of 8.38.

Table 3 Demographic Variables Statistic Analysis

Demographic variables analysis table (N=15)			
Gender	Male (14)	Female (1)	
	(93.3%)	(6.7%)	
Annual Income	Average	Standard Deviation	
	(15.13)	(8.38)	
The Average Annual Income of the Dragon and Lion Troupe	Below 200,000 NT (5)	200,000 – 500,000 NT (6)	More than 500,000 NT (4)
	(33.3%)	(40%)	(26.7%)
Whether there is a license or not	Licensed (12)	No Licensed (3)	
	(80%)	(20%)	
Number of Permanent Disciples	Average	Standard Deviation	
	(10.27)	(6.44)	
Whether The Position of the Head is Full- time	Full- time (10)	Part- time (5)	
	(66.7%)	(33.3%)	

With an average income distribution of the dragon and lion troupe below 200,000 there are 5 people (33.3%), 6 people having around 200,000 to 500,000 (40%), and over 500,000 there are only 4 people (26.7%). It is known that the salary level is less equal. The distribution of whether there are professional licenses is mainly divided into 12 people with own a license and only 3 people who do not own a license. Moreover, the average number of permanent disciples they have is 10 people. Those are the people who are working as full- time, and 5 people who work part-time with a total of 33.3 percent.

Figure 2 The Emotional Support Network Density Analysis Form

Indeed, subsequent to leading a semi-organized interview focusing on the 15 individuals from the Shiou Faction Lion Dance association. Had understood that in the part on daily reassurance, the informal community thickness is much higher than enlightening help. The outcome in Figure 2, demonstrates that the basic encouragement network thickness examination structure is far more powerful contrasted with the help from enlightening.

Figure 2, proves that the network density of emotional support is 0.47 and the standard deviation of the relationship in the network is 0.499. Meaning that the higher the network density it is the higher the connection relationship of the members is in social support. Especially, the network density is higher, the support is more influential among community members. With the support of the social network diagram in figure 3, the more line that connects, the better communication is.

Figure 3 Emotional Support in Social Network Diagram

The top three individuals in emotional support, with the highest external relationship centrality, can be found in A, I, and G in order. As for their standardized external relationship centrality is 100, 100, and 92.2 in order. The meaning of network density is an important attribute and property used to describe a network; in social network analysis, the term network density refers to a measure of the prevalence of dyadic linkage or direct tie within a social network [9]. In Figure 4, there is only 0.39 social network density with a standard deviation of 0.488. Compare to emotional support there's a 0.08 disparity in social network density. As well as a 0.011 gap in the standard deviation of the relationship in the network between emotional and informational support.

Figure 4 The Informational Support Network Density Analysis Form

In addition, Figure 5, of the social network of informational support shows that there is more gap between members. We can see that in the informational support aspect, the top three with the highest personal external relationship centrality are I, F, and G. And the standardized external relationship centrality is 100, 71.4, and 64.3 in order.

Figure 5 Informational Support in Social Network Diagram

6. Conclusion

To finish up, this paper centres around the interconnection of how individuals structure a relationship among the individuals, and how they participate and impart together, through the comprehension of triadic proportional determinism and social help. Particularly, realizing that profound and educational help gives out various implications to people. The finding and investigation showed that consistent reassurance is more valuable contrasted with instructive help. Since ready to deal with hierarchical issues, being able to intercede things, and orchestrating successive contacts, gatherings and social events can have a positive result. Paying attention to others' close to home words and intervening others' struggles can produce consistent reassurance inside the gatherings. Concerning the instructive help side, in spite of the fact that it can likewise impact the individuals it can't bring individuals closer.

By the by, the part shows the interpersonal organization densities of both profound and enlightening help. By contrasting the two viewpoints should be visible obviously that everyday reassurance is far more accommodating contrasted with instructive help. The justification behind this is that the Xiu School's improvement course is to accept non-material help as the principal objective. So by taking a gander at the finding and examination segments, the thickness of non-material (everyday encouragement) is way higher. This implies that non-material help for them implies much more than having genuine (instructive help) stuff. Since basic reassurance is tied in with giving self-compassion and trust, enlightening help is just about offering guidance. With the strong information of having an interpersonal organization chart, can see that for Xiu Pai, every one of the individuals had a cozy relationship with one another.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

References

- [1] N.d. [Internet]. Chinese Lion Dance, What is it and What does it Symbolized. 2022. Available from <https://www.chinahighlights.com/travelguide/special-report/chinese-new-year/new-year-lion-dance.htm>

- [2] Mossholder WK, Settoon PR, Henagan CS. A Relational Perspective on Turnover: Examining Structural, Attitudinal, and Behavioral Predictors. *Academy of Management Journal*. 2005; 45(4): 607- 18.
- [3] Bandura A. Social Learning Theory. *Canadian Journal of Sociology / Cahiers canadiens de sociologie*. 1977;2(3):321.
- [4] Pajares F, Frank & Usher, Ellen. Self-efficacy, motivation, and achievement in school from the perspective of reciprocal determinism. 10.1016/S0749-7423(08)15012-9. 2008.
- [5] Glanz K, Barbara K. R, Viswanath K. *Health Behavior and Health Education, Theory, Research, and Practice*. Edition 4th. 989 Market Street, San Francisco: Jossey- Bass A Wiley Imprint. 2008.
- [6] House JS. Work stress and social support [Internet]. *Open WorldCat*. Reading, Mass.: Addison-Wesley Pub. Co.; 1981 [cited 2022 Jul 11]. Available from: <https://www.worldcat.org/title/work-stress-and-social-support/oclc/654126161>
- [7] Folkways. A Study of the Sociological Importance of Usages, Manners, Customs, Mores, and Morals. By William Graham Sumner, Professor of Political and Social Science in Yale University. (Boston: Ginn and Company. 1907. Pp. v, 692.). *The American Historical Review*. 1907 Oct;
- [8] Bandura A. Social Cognitive Theory: An Agentic Perspective. *Annual Review of Psychology*. 2011; 52: 1-26.
- [9] Hu B. Network density. In B. Frey (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of educational research, measurement, and evaluation*. SAGE Publications, Inc. 2018; 1144-1145.